

ITS-Region Analysis for Medicinal Plants Identification

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ABSTRACT

The ITS (Internal Transcribed Spacer) region in nuclear ribosomal DNA can be used not only for species identification but also for taxonomic clarification. The advantage for using this region is that it is a small sequence 600-1000bp in length (vary from species to species) and can be used even from a less amount of sample. The other advantage is that it is present in multiple copies so that after PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) produce sufficient concentration for further downstream processing together with purification, Restriction digestion, RAPD-RFLP analysis, sequencing, etc. Therefore this region sequencing can be used for authentic identification of medicinal plants. Further restriction analysis will be helpful in solving the ambiguity. This paper deals with the use of bioinformatics tool for restriction analysis of ITS-region sequencing data.

Keyword: Medicinal plants; ITS region; PCR, Plant identification.

INTRODUCTION

The Internal transcribed Spacer is present in nuclear ribosomal DNA between 18S and 28S nrDNA region. This ITS region is removed during the processing of ribosomal RNA when forming the true functional ribosome that takes part in protein synthesis. In eukaryotes there are two ITS region present, ITS1 and ITS2. These two regions are separated by 5.8S RNA. (Fig 1)

Fig. 1: Internal transcribed spacer region

The sequence and restriction analysis of this region would be helpful to botanist and taxonomist to identify the correct plant at the molecular level without an error.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plants selected for the current work

The following eleven medicinal plants have been selected for the current study.

Santalum album L. (Santalaceae); *Pongamia pinnata* (L.) Pierre (Fabaceae); *Turnera ulmifolia* L.(Turneraceae); *Ricinus communis* L.(Euphorbiaceae); *Butea monosperma* (Lam.)Taub. Variety Monosperma (Fabaceae); *Xanthium indicum* Koen. (Asteraceae); *Cassia siamea* L. (Caesalpinaceae); *Piper nigrum* Linn.(Piperaceae); *Carica papaya* Linn. (Caricaceae); *Desmodium gangeticum* (L.) DC (Fabaceae); *Crotalaria juncea* L(Fabaceae)

DNA Extraction

The genomic DNA from the above mentioned plants was isolated using modified Khanuja method developed in our lab (1) and then purified with HiPurA spin kit.

PCR amplification

The polymerase chain reaction was carried out in 50µl reaction, containing 50ng of DNA template, 5µl 10X buffer, 3µl 25mM MgCl₂, 4µl 10mM dNTPs, 10pmoles of primers and 3 units/µl of Taq polymerase (Eppendorff). The universal ITS primers were used (Sigma) Forward (5'-GGAAGGAGAAGTCGTAACAAGG-3') and Reverse (5'TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3'). (Fig 2)

Purification of PCR Product (~700bp)

The purification was done with HiPurA spin kit.

Sequencing Data

All the sequencing reactions for described medicinal plants in both the direction (Forward and Reverse) are performed by Sanger method at Xcelris Labs Ltd. Ahmedabad, The sequencing data has been aligned and analysed with bioinformatic tools like Chromas lite and ApE software. The total number of base pair alignment in respective plants has shown below along with the restriction analysis. The number of sites present for the restriction enzymes are shown in bracket and the enzymes that are commonly presents in all the selected plants ITS region are highlighted. (Unpublished sequence data) (Table 1)

Table : 1 Restriction analysis

S.N.	Plant Name	Sequenced ITS region	Restriction sites	% GC
1	<i>Santalum album</i> L. (Santalaceae)	720bp	AccII(3); AflIII(1); AluI(2); Aval(1); BfmI(1); BseRI(1); BseSI(1); BsiEI(1); BsiYI(4); BspHI(1); BstAPI(1); Cac8I(5); ClaI(1); DpnI(2); DraII(2); EcoRV(1); HaeIII(2); HhaI(4); HpaII(1); Hpy188III(1); Hpy8I(1); Hpy99I(1); HpyCG4III(3); HpyCH4V(5); MaeII(1); MluI(1); MseI(2); MwoI(6); NlaIII(4); NlaIV(2); NspI(2); PpuMI(2); PvuI(1); SduI(1); StyI(2); TaqI(3); TspEI(1); TspGWI(3)	53%
2	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.)Pierre (Fabaceae)	622bp	AccII(4); AcyI(2); ApaLI(1); ApoI(1); Aval(1); BanII(1); BceAI(1); BsaAI(1); BseSI(2); BsiHKAI(1); BsiYI(3); BstBI(1); Bsu36I(1); Cac8I(4); ClaI(1); EcoRV(1); HaeIII(2); HhaI(5); HincII(2); HpaII(2); Hpy188III(3); Hpy8I(4); Hpy99I(1); HpyCH4III(2); HpyCH4V(3); MaeII(2); MwoI(4); NlaIII(2); NlaIV(1); PmlI(1); SduI(3); SmlI(2); StyI(1); TaqI(7); TspEI(3); TspGWI(1); XhoI(1)	55%
3	<i>Turnera ulmifolia</i> L. (Turneraceae)	603bp	AccBII(1); AccI(1); AccII(4); AcyI(2); Aval(1); BamHI(1); BanII(1); BbeI(1); BfmI(2); BseSI(1); BsiYI(4); Cac8I(5); CfrI(1); ClaI(1); DpnI(3); Eam1105I(1); EcoRV(1); HaeII(1); HaeIII(3); HhaI(7); HpaII(4); Hpy8I(3); Hpy99I(1); HpyCH4III(2); HpyCH4V(4); KasI(1); MaeII(1); MslI(1); MwoI(6); NarI(1); NlaIII(5); NlaIV(2); NsiI(1); OliI(1); PstI(1); SduI(2); SfoI(1); SmaI(1); StyI(1); TaqI(3); TspEI(1); TspGWI(1); Tth111I(1); XhoII(2); XmaI(1)	61%
4	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L. (Euphorbiaceae)	653bp	AccII(4); AflIII(2); Aval(1); BceAI(5); BfmI(2); BseSI(1); BsiEI(2); BsiHKAI(1); BsiYI(2); BspLU11I(1); BssHII(1); Bsu36I(1); Cac8I(7); CfrI(2); ClaI(1); EagI(2); Eam1105I(1); EcoRV(1); HaeIII(6); HhaI(7); HpaII(2); Hpy188III(3); Hpy99I(2); HpyCH4V(4); MfeI(1); MluI(1); MseI(1); MwoI(9); NcoI(1); NlaIII(5); NlaIV(2); NspI(3); PstI(1); RsaI(1); SduI(2); SmaI(1); SphI(2); StuI(1); StyI(2); TaqI(6); TspEI(4); TspGWI(1); XcmI(1); XhoI(1); XmnI(1)	59%
5	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.)Taub. Var. <i>Monosperma</i> (Fabaceae)	614bp	AccII(4); Aval(4); BceAI(3); BsaAI(1); BseRI(1); BseSI(1); BsiEI(3); BsiHKAI(1); BsiYI(6); BssHII(1); Cac8I(5); Cfr101(1); CfrI(2); ClaI(1); DpnI(2); DraII(1); EagI(1); EcoRV(1); HaeII(2); HaeIII(6); HhaI(5); HpaII(8); Hpy188III(6); Hpy8I(2); Hpy99I(2); HpyCH4III(2); HpyCH4V(2); MaeII(3); MspAII(1); MwoI(3); NlaIV(3); PmlI(1); PpuMI(1); SacII(1); SanDI(1); SduI(2); SmaI(2); SmlI(1); StyI(1); TaqI(5); TspEI(2); TspGWI(1); XhoI(1); XmaI(2)	62%
6	<i>Xanthium indicum</i> Koen. (Asteraceae)	651bp	AatII(1); AccII(3); AcyI(2); AflIII(2); AluI(2); ApaI(1); Aval(1); BanII(1); BceAI(1); BglI(1); BsaAI(2); BsaWI(1); BseSI(3); BsiEI(1); BsiYI(7); Bsp120I(1); BspLU11I(1); BstXI(1); BtrI(2); Cac8I(2); CfrI(1); ClaI(1); DpnI(2); DraII(1); Eam1105I(2); EcoRV(1); HaeIII(4); HhaI(3); HincII(1); HindIII(1); HpaII(2); Hpy8I(2); Hpy99I(1); HpyCH4III(3); HpyCH4V(2); MaeI(2); MaeII(8); MluI(1); MseI(2); MslI(1); MwoI(5); NcoI(1); NlaIII(3); NlaIV(1); NspI(1); PflMI(1); PvuI(1); RsaI(2); SduI(3); StuI(1); StyI(2); TaqI(3); TspEI(1); TspGWI(1); XcmI(1); ZraI(1)	55%
7	<i>Cassia siamea</i> L. (Caesalpiniaceae)	665bp	AccBII(1); AccII(5); AcyI(2); Aval(5); BamHI(1); BanII(2); BbeI(1); BsaWI(1); BseSI(2); BsiEI(1); BsiYI(3); BtrI(1); Cac8I(3); ClaI(1); DpnI(3); Eco47III(1); EcoRV(1); FspAI(1); FspI(1); HaeII(3); HaeIII(4); HhaI(7); HpaII(6); Hpy188III(1); Hpy8I(4); HpyCH4III(2); HpyCH4V(2); KasI(1); MaeI(2); MaeII(4); MseI(1); MwoI(5); NarI(1); NlaIII(1); NlaIV(4); NruI(1); SduI(4); SfoI(1); SmaI(1); SmlI(1); StyI(1); TaqI(5); TspEI(2); TspGWI(2); VspI(1); XcmI(1); XhoI(1); XhoII(1); XmaI(1)	60%
8	<i>Piper nigrum</i> Linn. (Piperaceae)	706bp	AccBII(2); AccII(5); AcyI(1); AflIII(1); AluI(1); Aval(1); BbeI(1); BceAI(1); BglI(1); BsaBI(1); BseRI(1); BseSI(2); BsiEI(1); BsiYI(6); BstBI(1); BtrI(1); Cac8I(7); CfrI(1); ClaI(1); EcoRV(2); FspI(1); HaeII(1); HaeIII(5); HhaI(8); HindIII(1); HpaII(1);	61%

			Hpy8I(1); Hpy99I(3); HpyCH4V(2); KasI(1); MaeII(2); MluI(1); MwoI(8); NarI(1); NlaIII(1); NlaIV(2); RsaI(1); SduI(2); SfoI(1); StuI(1); TaqI(7); TspEI(2); TspGWI(3)	
9	<i>Carica papaya</i> Linn. (Caricaceae)	580bp	AccII(13); AluI (1); AvaI(1); BceAI(2); BseSI(1); BsiEI(2); BsiHKAI(2); BsiYI(6); BssHII(2); BtrI(1); Cac8I(5); CfrI(1); ClaI(1); DpnI(1); EagI(1); Eam1105I(1); EcoRVI(1); HaeII(1); HaeIII(6); HhaI(10); HpaII(2); Hpy188III(1); Hpy8I(1); Hpy99I(2); HpyCH4III(1); HpyCH4V(1); MaeII(2); MspA1I(2); MwoI(8); NlaIV(2); RsaI(1); SacII(1); SduI(3); SmaI(1); TaqI(3); TspEI(2); TspGWI(2); Tth111I(1); XmaI(1)	66%
10	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> (L.)DC (Fabaceae)	581bp	AccBII(1); AccII(7); AcyI(2); AflIII(1); ApaLI(2); AvaI(2); BceAI(3); BseRI(1); BseSI(4); BsiHKAI(2); BsiYI(8); BspLU11I(1); Cac8I(6); Cfr10I(1); ClaI(3); DpnI(1); DraII(1); EcoRV(1); HaeIII(6); HhaI(4); HpaII(5); Hpy8I(4); Hpy99I(2); HpyCH4III(2); HpyCH4V(3); MaeII(1); MspA1I(2); MwoI(2); NlaIII(2); NlaIV(5); NspI(1); PflMI(1); PpuMI(1); SacII(2); SanDI(1); SduI(4); SmaI(2); StyI(2); TaqI(3); TspEI(1); XmaI(2)	60%
11	<i>Crotalaria juncea</i> L. (Fabaceae)	644bp	AccBII(3); AccII(1); AcyI(1); AflIII(2); AluI(2); BanII(1); BbeI(1); BseSI(1); BsiYI(3); BspLU11I(1); BstAPI(1); BstBI(1); BstXI(1); Cac8I(5); Cfr10I(1); ClaI(1); DpnI(3); DraII(1); DraIII(1); EcoRV(1); HaeII(2); HaeIII(1); HhaI(4); HindIII(1); HpaII(2); Hpy188III(1); Hpy8I(2); HpyCH4III(3); HpyCH4V(2); KasI(1); MaeI(2); MaeII(1); MluI(1); MslI(1); MwoI(3); NarI(1); NlaIII(3); NlaIV(5); NspI(1); OliI(1); PpuMI(1); RsaI(1); SduI(2); SfoI(1); SmlI(1); StyI(2); TaqI(4); TatI(1); TspEI(2); TspGWI(2)	57%

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

With the use of ITS region sequencing data, one can easily identify the medicinal plant at the molecular level. Also the restriction pattern is helpful in further confirmation of the result.

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